

The James
Hutton
Institute

Greenspace quality metrics: Scoping Review protocol

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Amendments

30th April 2022 – Version 1 protocol complete

Support

RESAS SRP 2022-2027 C6-1 Reciprocal care for nature and wellbeing

Role in protocol development

- Provided definitions for 'greenspace'
- Fed into key word selection
- Identified additional greenspace organisations to search
- Added to data to be extracted.

Introduction

Background

Increasing access to the outdoors is a Scottish Government National Performance Framework indicator. Encouraging, managing and investing in outdoor access, including urban and rural greenspaces, has cross-sectoral policy significance relating to health, planning, environment, education and tourism. Recent work on the benefits of particularly urban greenspace has identified quality as of more importance than quantity (Dobson et al. 2019). Despite ongoing interest in the characterisation of spatial qualities of greenspaces, definitions and indicators of environmental quality are seldom uniform. Understanding how ‘quality’ of greenspaces is measured in relation to the multifunctionality of these places will therefore contribute to improving management, policy and decision making to produce better outcomes.

Stakeholder engagement

Project proposal stage involved input from: RESAS; NatureScot; Public Health Scotland (PHS); Cairngorms National Park Authority (CNPA); Growing Up in Scotland (GUS).

Keywords identification – NatureScot (overview of greenspace types), Greenspace Scotland (focus on urban greenspaces) and Public Health Scotland (focus on health and wellbeing).

Identifying sources of grey literature - RESAS, NatureScot, Greenspace Scotland – all have wide overview of policy and reports

Data extracted – RESAS, NatureScot – wide overview policy needs and existing knowledges.

Objectives

1. Identify which quality indicators are currently being used for greenspaces, with particular focus on outcomes for the “Four Capitals”¹:
 - a. Environment – natural capital (potential indicators: biodiversity, water, air, soil)
 - b. Community – social capital (potential indicators: group meeting spaces, demonstration of shared values)
 - c. People – Human capital (e.g. health and wellbeing potential indicators: gym equipment, air quality)
 - d. Business – financial capital (potential indicators: cafes, nature tours)
2. Understand how multifunctionality of greenspace is being captured in greenspace quality metrics

Methods

Eligibility criteria

Criteria	Eligibility
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¹ Based on the “Four Capitals” approach proposed as part of the “Wellbeing Economy of Scotland” (Advisory Group on Economic Recovery, 2020)

Population	Direct and indirect users of greenspace services
Intervention	NA
Comparator	NA
Outcome	NA
Study design	Qualitative or quantitative studies, excluding natural science lab-based studies, review and opinion pieces, or in which data has not been analysed.
Setting	Greenspaces, rural and urban, as defined below. In the following countries: United Kingdom, Ireland, Norway, The Netherlands, Belgium, Germany, Denmark, Luxemburg, France, Austria, and Poland. These countries are chosen because they are within the same biome (temperate deciduous forest) and within Europe. Geographic focus was constrained by biome and culture, thus, quality indicators found in this literature are likely to have greatest relevance for Scotland. For further information see Appendix A.
Language	English
Publication status	Published and grey literature, excluding pre-prints
Publication years	Within 5 years
Greenspace definition	“vegetated areas and blue spaces in both urban and rural areas, including woodland, parks, farmland, paths and beaches and other aquatic environments that are publicly accessible” – following communication with funder.
Environment definition	Natural capital – stock of natural assets, including soil, air, water and biodiversity which may occur in, or be influenced by, greenspace (Advisory Group on Economic Recovery, 2020)
Community definition	Social capital – networks, shared experience, values and understanding which may occur in, or be influenced by, greenspace (Advisory Group on Economic Recovery, 2020)
People definition	Human capital – health and wellbeing accumulated through greenspace use or as a result of greenspace in the surrounding area (e.g. air quality is improved as a result of nearby greenspace, regardless of whether an individual actively uses it) (Advisory Group on Economic Recovery, 2020)
Business definition	Financial capital – monetary gain through greenspace use or association (Advisory Group on Economic Recovery, 2020)
Quality definition	Only considering quality of direct services from greenspaces, which have a link to the Four Capitals.

Information sources

Database	Rationale
Web of Science	Covering range of academic literature
Websites of Scottish greenspace managers (NatureScot, RSPB, Greenspace Scotland, National Trust Scotland, Game and Wildlife Conservation Trust, Forest Research, Scottish Forestry, Woodland Trust, Scottish Wildlife Trust, Keep Scotland Beautiful, SEPA, Historic Environment Scotland, Royal Caledonian Horticultural Society, John Muir Trust, COSLA, Edinburgh and Lothian Greenspace Trust, Glasgow Clyde Valley Greenspace Partnership, Green Action Trust, Central Scotland Green Network, The Conservation Volunteers, Fields Trust,	Grey literature

Seven Lochs, Green Infrastructure Intervention, Mountaineering Scotland, Scottish Land and Estates, Ramblers)	
Website of Scottish Government	Government funded reports

Search strategy

Topic	Potential Keywords
Greenspace	greenspace OR "green space" OR park* OR wood* OR forest* OR mountain* OR hill* OR farm* OR playspace OR "playpark" OR "green corridor" OR allotment OR "community garden" OR "burial ground*" OR churchyard OR cemetery OR "playing field" OR "sustainable urban drainage systems" OR "open space" OR "green infrastructure" OR "green networks"
Bluespace	beach* OR coast* OR lake* OR river* OR canal* OR loch OR burn OR stream
Quality	Quality OR condition OR "fit* for purpose" OR evaluat*
Environment	biodivers* OR "species rich*" OR ecolog* OR "climate change" OR sustainab* OR conservation OR "natural capital" OR "nature based solution*"
Community	community OR "shar* values" OR "meeting space*" OR "group activit*" OR neighbourhood OR volunteer*
People	health OR wellbeing OR "physical activity" OR disab* OR mental
Business	financ* OR econom* OR agr?tourism OR ecotourism OR "agricultural tourism" OR enterprise
Location	"United Kingdom" OR UK OR England OR Wales OR Scotland OR Ireland OR Norway OR Netherlands OR Belgium OR Germany OR Denmark OR Luxemburg OR France OR Austria OR Poland

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((TS=(greenspace OR "green space" OR park* OR wood* OR forest* OR mountain* OR hill* OR farm* OR playspace OR "playpark" OR "green corridor" OR allotment OR "community garden" OR "burial ground*" OR churchyard OR cemetery OR "playing field" OR "sustainable urban drainage systems" OR "open space" OR "green infrastructure" OR "green networks" OR beach* OR coast* OR lake* OR river* OR canal* OR loch OR burn OR stream))

AND TS=(Quality OR condition OR "fit* for purpose" OR evaluat*))

AND TS=(biodivers* OR "species rich*" OR ecolog* OR "climate change" OR sustainab* OR conservation OR "natural capital" OR "nature based solution*" OR community OR "shar* values" OR "meeting space*" OR "group activit*" OR neighbourhood OR volunteer* OR health OR wellbeing OR "physical activity" OR disab* OR mental OR financ* OR econom* OR agr?tourism OR ecotourism OR "agricultural tourism" OR enterprise)

Study records

Data management

Papers will be stored in a shared OneDrive folder by first author name followed by date. If there are multiple papers with the same first author name and date they will be given letters following the alphabet (e.g. Smith2010a, Smith2010b). This will form the paper ID code.

Data will be extracted into Excel datasheets, linked to papers by paper ID code. All entries will include initials of person adding data to the sheet.

Selection process

Title screening

Following searches records will be combined and duplicates removed. Titles will then be screened based on eligibility criteria. Titles will be excluded if they:

- Do not include greenspaces
- Include only greenspaces outside of our geographical area of interest (United Kingdom, Ireland, Norway, The Netherlands, Belgium, Germany, Denmark, Luxemburg, France, Austria, and Poland)
- Are not concerned with natural, social, human or financial capital
- Are review or opinion pieces
- Do not consider analysis of data
- Are natural science lab-based studies (i.e. including experiments in economics or psychology labs)
- Are in a language other than English

If there is any ambiguity papers will be retained to abstract screening.

Abstract screening

Abstracts will be screened according to eligibility criteria as above. Retained papers will also be classified according to the types of capital considered (natural, social, human, financial), green or blue space, and urban, rural or island, and qualitative, quantitative or mixed methods.

Full text screening

Full text will be screened at the same time as data extracted according to eligibility criteria detailed above.

At all stages 10% of papers will be screened by all researchers involved in search and Kappa statistic used to determine agreement in retaining/excluding papers. Where disagreement is high, papers will be reconsidered and discussed until agreement between researchers is reached. The reason for paper exclusion will be recorded in each instance.

Data collection process

Data will be extracted following abstract screening into Excel sheet. The sheet will be piloted with 10 of the same records by each researcher to allow adaptations as needed and to check consistency in data extracted.

Where data are not available from literature the corresponding author will be contacted. If data cannot be obtained it will be considered “not available” and therefore not counted towards the strength of evidence.

Data items

Article metadata

Title

Author

Year

Publication

Study context

Country

Exact location – as described

Urban – Y/N

Scottish Government Urban greenspace typology – Public park or garden, amenity greenspace, playspace, sports area, green corridor, natural/semi-natural, allotment or community growing space, civic space, burial grounds, other functional greenspace

Island – Y/N

Habitat type – Forest, Grassland, Urban greenspace, Agriculture, Coastal, Lake/Loch, Linear waterbody, Mountain

Number of sites

Total area of sites

Start year data collection

End year data collection

Duration data collection (months)

Capitals

Environment – Y/N

Describe environment considered

Community – Y/N

Describe community considered

People – Y/N

Describe people considered

Business – Y/N

Describe business considered

Multiple capitals considered – Y/N

Does paper explicitly identify multiple capitals? - Y/N

How? – as described in paper

Quality

Quality indicator used – As described

Multiple indicators used – Y/N

Population identified – Y/N

Population described – As described

Quality of indicator tested – Y/N

Method used to test quality of indicator – as described in paper

Outcome of quality testing – As described

Other WPs

Is this paper considering young people – Y/N
 Is this paper considering nature capabilities -Y/N
 Is this paper exploring barriers/constraints to use – Y/N

Data synthesis

Data will be synthesised based on type of capital considered. Further synthesis will look at where indicators cross categories, split between green and blue space (and potentially habitat type), rural, urban and island.

Outcomes, risk of bias, critical appraisal and prioritisation

Will not be carried out.

Gantt Chart

	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar
Protocol	■	■										
Develop search string - academic		■										
Search grey literature		■										
Screen titles			■									
Design database			■									
Screen abstracts				■	■							
Extract data						■	■	■				
Evidence map finalised including report									■	■	■	

References

Advisory Group on Economic Recovery, 2020, Towards a robust, resilient wellbeing economy for Scotland, Report of the Advisory Group on Economic Recovery, Accessed from: [https://www.gov.scot/publications/towards-robust-resilient-wellbeing-economy-scotland-report-advisory-group-economic-recovery/documents/]

Dobson, J., Harris, C., Eadson, W., and Gore, T. (2019). Space to thrive: A rapid evidence review of the benefits of parks and green spaces for people and communities. The National Lottery Heritage Fund and The National Lottery Community Fund, London.

Appendix A- Rationale for geographic focus of WP1

The following countries were chosen for the literature review:
 United Kingdom, Ireland, Norway, The Netherlands, Belgium, Germany, Denmark, Luxemburg, France, Austria, and Poland.

These countries were chosen because they were within the same main geographical biome as Scotland and the UK (see figure 1), and they were within Europe. Ecology and biogeography highlight how biotic communities of flora are apparent on spatial and temporal scales (Mucina, 2019). These biotic communities are known as biomes.

The countries highlighted above are within the temperate deciduous forest biome, with the exemption of Norway. However, Norway has cultural similarities to Scotland, particularly in rural and island communities (Bryden, 2015; Ankamah-Yeboah et al., 2020). Additionally, there is significant literature exploring greenspace quality in Norway (Fongar et al., 2019). For these two reasons, it is included in the countries studied.

Moreover, this research has chosen to focus solely on Europe, chiefly due to the cultural similarities. However, this focus is also because the larger countries, such as the United States, that share in part the temperate deciduous forest biome, also include several other biomes, which make up significant parts of their land mass (Mucina, 2019). Thus, it would be difficult to explore literature solely from this biome.

The choice to constrain the countries study by shared biome allows the exploration of similar greenspace ecology. This is important as it ensures the literature will have the greatest relevance for a Scottish context, with quality indicators from countries sharing this biome more likely to be appropriate for a Scottish context than indicators from tropical shrubland, for example.

Figure 1, biomes across the world, as modelled by BIOME4 (Kaplan et al., 2003). Reproduced from: Paleoclimate Modelling Intercomparison Project II (<http://pmip2.lsce.ipsl.fr/synth/biome4.shtml>).

Bibliography

Ankamah-Yeboah, I., et al. (2020). "Public Perceptions of Deep-Sea Environment: Evidence From Scotland and Norway." *Frontiers in Marine Science* 7.

Bryden, J. (2015). *Northern Neighbours: Scotland and Norway since 1800*, Edinburgh University Press.

Fongar, C., et al. (2019). "Does Perceived Green Space Quality Matter? Linking Norwegian Adult Perspectives on Perceived Quality to Motivation and Frequency of Visits." *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 16(13): 2327.

Kaplan, J. O., et al. (2003). "Climate change and Arctic ecosystems: 2. Modeling, paleodata-model comparisons, and future projections." *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres* 108(D19).

Mucina, L. (2019), Biome: evolution of a crucial ecological and biogeographical concept. *New Phytol*, 222: 97-114. <https://doi.org/10.1111/nph.15609>